

Promoting Financial Inclusion through Financial Education - Global Trends and Georgia

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Abstract

One of the objectives of the UN Sustainable Development Goals is to build an inclusive society, and no country should be left behind in this process. However, since the Sustainable Development Goals do not include financial inclusion directly, most of the goals that integrate economic and social areas cannot be achieved without financial inclusion. This is why promoting financial inclusion is at the top of the agenda of policymakers around the world today.

Financial literacy and financial inclusion, along with other financial sector consumer protection mechanisms and regulations, empower individuals and play an important role in the stability of a country's financial system. Financial literacy provides people with the knowledge and skills needed to manage money efficiently. Financially educated citizens, who know how to make the necessary decisions without losing much, are a strong pillar of the country's economy.

Despite the importance of financial literacy, numerous studies confirm that a large part of the world's population still suffers from financial illiteracy. According to the results of the S&P Global FinLit Survey conducted in 2015, only one out of three adults (33 percent of adults) were financially literate worldwide. This means that approximately 3.5 billion adults globally (most of them from developing countries) do not understand basic financial concepts. The issue has become even more urgent under the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic, and additional, effective steps in this direction should be taken by the governments and central banks of the countries.

This paper presents a study of the causal relationships between financial education and the degree of financial inclusion, which is conducted based on the analysis of the results of studies conducted by international and local financial organizations.

Keywords: financial education, financial literacy, financial inclusion, inclusive growth, sustainable development.

Introduction

Financial education and financial inclusion, along with a strong framework for consumer protection in the financial sector, are essential for empowering individuals and can contribute to both the stability of a country's financial system and the inclusive growth and development of the economy (OECD/INFE, 2020) In contrast to exclusive economic growth, which benefits only a few individuals within a narrow group of society, inclusive development benefits the wider strata of society. The result of inclusive economic growth affects every citizen of the country and has not only a quantitative but also a qualitative effect (Lasha Arevadze, 2015)

Bringing forward the issue of inclusive growth was caused by the fact that in some countries, rapid economic growth did not lead to a reduction in inequality (Kasradze & Zarnadze, CHALLENGES OF ECONOMIC OF GEORGIA: GOOD AND BAD ECONOMIC GROWTH, 2019). The issue

has become even more urgent under the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic and the need to take additional steps in this direction on the part of the governments and central banks of the countries has arisen, because a large part of the citizens did not have enough financial education and resilience to cope with the pressure of the economic and financial crisis caused by the pandemic and to resolve effectively their issues related to daily financial decisions (Kasradze Tea, 2020).

The aim of the presented work is to study the influence of financial education on the quality of financial inclusion and determine the cause-and-effect relationships between them based on the analysis of studies conducted by various scientists, international financial and local organizations.

In particular, the results of the research on financial education and financial inclusion of the International Financial Education Network of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the results of the World Bank's global financial inclusion research, the series of working documents of the Asian Development Bank Institute and the results of the research about financial literacy by the ISET Policy Institute and TBC Bank were studied and analyzed in the paper, also local policy documents, legal acts and works of Georgian and foreign researchers.

Literature Review

"The economic policy of the past decade was close to the paradigm known as the "Washington Consensus", which implies an emphasis on macroeconomic stabilization and the facilitation of private investment through the implementation of large-scale infrastructural projects, resulting in economic growth. And according to the logic of Kuznetsian economic development, economic growth will eventually lead to overcoming the problem of inequality" (Lasha Arevadze, 2015) However, in the later period, skepticism towards the "Washington Consensus" increased, which was mostly related to its theoretical character. The logic of the "Washington Consensus" has also been removed from the economic policy of the World Bank, and today it is clearly dominated by the so-called Paradigm of "inclusive growth" (Lasha Arevadze, 2015).

The paradigm of inclusive growth was reflected in the socio-economic development strategy of Georgia - "Georgia 2020", in which we read that the economic policy of the last decade was successful in terms of attracting investments and promoting short-term economic growth, however, it failed to create a basis for increasing the competitiveness of the Georgian economy and long-term inclusive economic growth. The results of economic growth were not reflected on a large part of the population of Georgia, nor did it have a significant impact on the reduction of unemployment and poverty rates (Government of Georgia, 2014).

The reason for this is the low competitiveness of the private sector, inadequately developed human capital and limited access to financial resources. All of the above leads to financial inclusion, the most important contributing factor of which is financial education. Economic inclusion and inclusive growth are unthinkable without financial inclusion (Kasradze, Tea, 2018).

"Stable and high economic growth is a necessary condition for us to be able to help the most vulnerable groups who work hard to belong to the middle class. They should also be able to benefit from the positive results of the economy," says Bill Morneau, adding: "But to ensure inclusive economic growth, we must make sure that families have the knowledge and fully use the opportunities that lead to their maximum involvement in the economy" (Morneau, 2016). To accomplish this task, Morneau places particular emphasis on financial education and keeping step with innovation.

Financial literacy is an important factor in people's lives because it provides people with the knowledge and skills needed to manage money effectively. Decisions and actions taken without it have no solid foundation for success, and the results are dire: 40% of Americans can't afford \$400 in emergency expenses, credit card debt is at an all-time high, and it's no surprise that nearly two-thirds of Americans fail a basic financial literacy test. (Rose, 2020).

Despite the importance of financial literacy, many studies indicate that a large part of the world's population still suffers from financial illiteracy, and it is necessary to take measures to correct the problem (Potrich, Vieira, & Kirch, 2015)

The essence of financial literacy involves learning to choose between multiple alternatives for setting financial goals. Governments all over the world are interested in finding effective approaches to increase the level of financial literacy of the population, creating or improving its national strategy, offering learning opportunities (Potrich, Vieira, & Kirch, 2015).

In 2016, the National Bank of Georgia approved the "National Strategy of Financial Education of Georgia", which aims to raise the level of financial education of the population of Georgia, which will ultimately become a prerequisite for improving its financial well-being and protecting the consumers' rights" (National Bank of Georgia, 2016)

According to the document, the strategic directions are increasing knowledge about the usefulness of financial education; enhancing coordination and cooperation among stakeholders; expanding opportunities for education. The basis for developing the strategy was the study of financial education and involvement, which was carried out at the initiative of the National Bank of Georgia. The research methodology is based on the OECD/INFE International Network for Financial Education of the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development 2015 Guidelines for Measuring Financial Education and Financial Inclusion (Sonari, 2016). As a result of the mentioned research, it was possible to derive the score of financial education of the population of Georgia, which includes three components, financial knowledge - maximum 7 points, financial behavior - maximum 9 points and financial attitude - maximum 5 points. On a 21-point scale, the financial education score of the population of Georgia is 12.3. According to the components, it breaks down as follows: financial knowledge - 4.5, financial behavior - 5 and financial attitude - 2.8 points.

Within the framework of the mentioned strategy the following target groups with a high need for financial education were defined: young generation - students and pupils; unemployed population; persons employed in large companies and organizations; villagers and people facing specific life moments.

Financial inclusion implies the process of promoting affordable, timely and adequate access to a wide range of regulated financial products and services to widen their use by all sections of society through tailored existing and innovative approaches, including financial awareness and education to achieve financial well-being and promote economic and social inclusion (Atkinson & Messy, 2013).

Financial inclusion is a two-way process: in terms of delivery, it requires the provision of appropriate financial instruments, and in terms of demand - knowledge of this product (OECD/INFE, 2020). According to the World Bank's approach, financial inclusion is not only about access to financial resources. For the general public and SMEs it is a much broader concept and includes widespread access to quality financial instruments and services, including loans, deposit services, insurance, pensions and payment systems, as well as financial education and

consumer rights protection mechanisms. This approach once again emphasizes the reciprocity of the process of financial inclusion: in order for a wide range of quality financial instruments to be presented on the market (Kasradze Tea, 2021), based on a simple market principle, the order must come from the society, which is determined by the level of financial education of the society (Kasradze, Tea; Zarnadze, Nino, 2018).

Research on Financial Inclusion and Financial Education in Georgia

According to the 2020 International Survey of Adult Financial Literacy conducted by the International Network for Financial Education of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD/INFE), indicators of financial inclusion are defined in the context of product knowledge and choices based on this knowledge, these indicators are: knowledge of at least 5 financial products, buying financial products last year and referring family/friends for loans/savings. The research was conducted in 26 countries and economics of Asia, Europe and Latin America (12 of these countries are members of the OECD).

According to the research results, about 83% of the respondents knew at least 5 financial products on average. In terms of countries, it should be noted that according to the first indicator, 100% is recorded in China and Germany. Among the participating countries, the lowest rate is recorded in Colombia - 49%. In Georgia, this indicator is 84%.

Globally, 46% of the respondents purchased a financial product last year. In terms of countries, the highest rate of this indicator - 89% is recorded in Indonesia, and the lowest - in Italy - 23%. In Georgia, this indicator is 47%.

Diagram N1.

Indicators of financial inclusion

Base: all respondents. % included on each measure. Multiple categories possible. Sorted by "Bought a product in the past year".

Note: Derived variables; France, Russia and Thailand have not provided financial inclusion data. There is no data for product awareness for Italy. The OECD member countries in the sample are: Austria, Colombia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Korea, Poland, Portugal and Slovenia.

Source: OECD/INFE 2020 International Survey of Adult Financial Literacy

As for the third indicator, it aims to find out the extent to which people turn to family members and friends for financial services that can be provided by the financial sector. Although the support of family members and friends includes many potential benefits, it also includes risks. This indicator can also show us the level of informality of the financial sector involved in the economy. In this regard, the fact that the highest share - 46% is recorded in Georgia, which is twice as much as the global average indicator, which is 23%, is especially notable.

The trend of borrowing money from family members and friends is growing in Georgia. In 2011, this figure was 14%, in 2014 - 16%, in 2017 - 20%, and in 2020 - 46%. From 2011 to 2020, the indicator increased by 32%. In order to identify the reasons for the tendency of loans to move to the informal sector, it is important to consider the debt burden. The results of a study commissioned by the National Bank of Georgia showed that middle-income households, whose income ranges from 551 to 900 GEL, have the highest debt Payment to Income ratio (PTI) and are therefore the most burdened with current liabilities (Sonari, 2016) This may be one of the determining factors of the revealed trend. It should also be taken into account that since 2018, the SEB has started to introduce important regulatory tools, including determining the maximum limits of the loan service ratio (PTI) according to the categories of income amount, and there is a high probability that loans will be transferred to a sector where solvency tests are not carried out.

According to global data, despite the progress achieved in recent years, the use of financial technologies in Georgia still remains a challenge and lags significantly behind the regional average. According to the World Bank's Financial Inclusion Survey in 2014, adults who owned debit cards accounted for 39.7% of the population, which is 10% below the average data of Europe and Central Asia (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019)). Researches use different categories of indicators to measure financial inclusion, such as: access indicators (number of ATMs, number of bank branches per thousand inhabitants, branches of tax service providers), distribution indicators (geographical and demographic penetration of financial services), utilization indicators (number of credit and debit accounts, deposit volume and giving credits to SMEs and households, etc.) and qualitative indicators (privacy requirements, dispute resolution and cost of use) (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019).

In terms of access indicators, Georgia is a leader among the countries of the South Caucasus both in the number of commercial bank branches (diagram N2) per 100,000 adults, and in the number of ATMs (diagram N3). The network of payment service providers (PSP) is also developing quite quickly, the number of PSP branches has increased from 641 to 1769 in five years (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019) .

In terms of distribution indicators, financial inclusion is improved by increasing the availability of bank branches and ATMs even outside the three big cities of Georgia (Tbilisi, Rustavi, Kutaisi). From 2005 to 2016, the number of bank branches outside the three mentioned cities increased from 141 to 427, and ATMs - from 31 to 674. However, a significant share of the population in the regions of Georgia remains a category that does not have access to financial services. The largest part of financial services is concentrated in three large cities - 70% of ATMs available nationwide, and 56% of bank branches, while 36.5% of Georgia's population lives in these cities (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019).

Diagram N2.

Branches of Commercial Banks per 100,000 Adults in the South Caucasus

Source: Financial Access Survey, WB.

Diagram N3.

The Number of ATMs per 100,000 Adults in the South Caucasus Countries

Source: Financial Access Survey, WB.

As for utilization indicators in terms of deposit and savings accounts, according to 2017 data, a rather low inclusion rate is recorded in the 15-24 age group - 46.1%, while the average rate for all middle-income countries is 50.7%, and in European and Central Asian countries this rate is 56.3%. As for deposit and savings accounts, in terms of gender, Georgia leads the way in terms of women, and the participation rate is 63.6%, which is higher than the rate of Europe and Central Asia - 62.5%, and the rate of middle-income countries - 53%. (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019).

According to the survey of the World Bank's Global Financial Inclusion, people who do not have an account name the following reasons: distance from financial institutions - 5.6%; the cost of financial services - 12.7%; insufficient finances - 53%; lack of necessary documents - 37.2%; lack of trust in financial institutions - 20.1%; do not need financial services - 2%; religious reasons - 2.6%; somebody in the family has an account - 34.5%.

Georgia is also a leader in the South Caucasus region in terms of access to credit (Diagram 4), although the increase in the household loan service ratio carries certain risks. From 2013 to 2017, loans issued by microfinance organizations secured by real and movable property increased 5 times, which were mostly denominated in US dollars and increased default risks due to the mismatch between household income and liabilities (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019).

Diagram N4.

Getting Credit: Distance from the Frontier in the South Caucasus Countries

Source: G-20 Financial Inclusion Indicators.

The rapid growth of Georgian consumer credit has raised concerns about the sustainability of credit expansion. Access to credit was not a major concern until 2018, but the situation required attention in terms of borrowers' safety and informed choice. Since 2018, the Government of Georgia and the National Bank of Georgia have demanded stricter consumer protection measures, de-dollarization

of SME loans, and increased efforts to improve financial education that will improve the financial inclusion rate.

Stakeholders such as commercial banks, international financial institutions and the National Bank of Georgia see financial education as the key to improving financial well-being for households in Georgia (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019)

Along with the OECD/INFE international study of financial literacy competences of adults, which made it possible to derive the financial education score of the population of Georgia (12.3 points on a 21-point scale), the results of a study conducted by the ISET Policy Institute in 2016 together with TBC are also interesting. The sample consisted of 1,000 respondents and the questions assessed knowledge about interest rates, inflation, financial risks and effective interest rates. According to the results of the study, only 5.8% of the respondents answered all four questions correctly, 42% were in the moderate range, and 52% showed a low level of financial knowledge, although only 14% of them admit a lack of knowledge in finance. It is also worth noting that there is a close correlation between financial education and general education - 78% of the respondents who answered the questions correctly had a university degree or equivalent, while the respondents who often answered: "I don't know" had primary or secondary education. A big difference can be seen regionally as well - 81% of the respondents with high financial education are from the capital. From the results of this research, the trust in the banking sector is also worth noting. 79% of the respondents trust commercial banks unconditionally, although 85% distrust other unregulated financial institutions (Diagram N5) (Asian Development Bank Institute, 2019). In order to improve the quality of inclusiveness in this direction, various regulatory mechanisms have been introduced by the NBG, including mandatory deposit insurance from January 1, 2018, which in the conditions of low indicators of financial education are more likely to guarantee an increase in trust in financial institutions than the introduction of Basel III within the regulatory framework.

Diagram N5

Source: ISET-PI TBC Financial Literacy Survey.

As already mentioned, financial inclusion is a rather broad concept and it includes long-term planning in terms of pension provision as well. In this regard, the results of the research conducted by the ISET Policy Institute and TBC on financial education show that only 12.4% of the respondents make savings for old age, and 14.3% think that they will be completely dependent on the state basic pension, which is equal to the living wage.

Diagram N6

of respondents: 1000.
 Source: ISET-PI TBC Financial Literacy Survey.

According to the 2020 International Adult Financial Literacy Survey conducted by OECD/INFE, respondents were identified using a combination of four indicators. These are: savings, investment and pension products, which are not mandatory; payment products or transaction accounts (except credit cards); insurance products (auto, health, personal liability, property, etc.); credit products (any official bank loan or pledge).

According to the research results, payment products are the most widespread. On average, 70% of the respondents report owning such products (more than 80% for OECD 11), 51% of the respondents own savings, investment or pension products, 44% own credit products and 37% - insurance products (for OECD 11 about 50%). In Georgia, this indicator is quite low - 13%. Only 42% of the respondents in Georgia own payment products. In the category of insurance products this figure is 10% of adults. A relatively better rate is recorded in the category of credit savings, investments and pension products - (39%).

Diagram N7

Product holding

Base: all respondents. % of respondents holding each type of product; sorted by "Payment product".

In this paper, we repeatedly reiterated that financial education is an important lever for increasing financial inclusion. To illustrate this, according to the OECD/INFE 2020 survey results, we present statistical data on financial knowledge and ownership of financial products, showing trends in attitudes that are seen between these variables.

Diagram N8

Financial knowledge score, as a percentage of maximum, by number of products held

Base: all respondents. Financial knowledge score of adults split by product holding, as a percent of maximum score. Maximum financial knowledge score is 7.

As we can see from the diagram, in relation to the score of financial knowledge, it is brought into compliance with the number of products owned from the set of financial products discussed above. In other words, in those countries where the financial education score of the maximum score (7 points) is 46% of the given set, on average, they do not own any of them, in the case of 56% they own one financial product, and in the case of more than 66% they own more than one product.

In Table 1 below, the data are presented individually, by countries Table N1

Financial knowledge score (% of maximum, by number of products held)

All respondents. Financial knowledge score of adults split by product holding, as a percent of maximum score. Maximum financial knowledge score is 7.

	holds no products	holds one product	holds more products
Austria	66	62	77
Bulgaria	43	56	71
Colombia	53	55	59
Croatia	44	55	70
Czech Republic	36	54	68
Estonia	57	65	76
Georgia	58	64	73
Germany		78	74
Hong Kong, China			88
Hungary	57	62	71
Indonesia	40	50	59
Italy	41	55	71
Korea	53	50	68
Malaysia	29	44	55
Malta	28	29	32
Moldova	53	63	65
Montenegro	54	50	63
Peru	52	58	62
Poland	47	62	76
Portugal	33	46	63
North Macedonia	45	53	61
Romania	40	50	54
Slovenia		61	70
Average (total sample)	46	56	66

Note: Missing data in this table indicates that in some economies there were no individuals who fall into the relevant category of product holding. For example, in Germany all individuals responded they hold at least one product.

According to the results of the research conducted by the National Bank of Georgia based on the OECD/INFE methodology, the score of financial knowledge as a component of financial education in Georgia is 4.5, which is 64.29% of its maximum value. Therefore, we can say that according to the average indicator, each adult in Georgia owns at least one of the given set of products.

The goal of financial education is to better prepare people to manage their money, achieve their financial goals, and avoid the stress associated with financial problems, thereby improving their financial well-being. The problems of financial sustainability were clearly revealed in the conditions of the Covid 19 pandemic. The outcome of financial education, along with financial well-being, is the financial resilience needed to provide individuals with predictable financial choices and coping with life's challenges. Financial resilience also protects individuals from unpredictable shocks such as the Covid 19 pandemic (OECD/INFE, 2020).

Financial sustainability of individuals consists of six main elements: taking control of money; taking care of expenses; existence of a financial buffer; overcoming financial deficit; individual financing plan; fraud awareness (OECD/INFE, 2020).

The measures taken to limit the spread of Covid 19 have had a strong negative impact on business activity and the financial stability and well-being of individuals. Among the elements of financial resilience, it is especially important to have a financial buffer during unpredictable shocks, which includes the existence of available savings and the ability to provide oneself for periods of time when significant incomes don't exist.

As part of the OECD/INFE 2020 survey, the survey participants were asked about the length of time they could support themselves in case of losing their main source of income without borrowing

money or replacing a place of residence. The results are highly heterogeneous across countries and economics (Diagram N9). Georgia is one of those countries that are characterized by unfavorable results. According to the results of the survey, 50% of the respondents name this period as one week or less, 37% - from 1 to 6 months, 7% - 6 months or more and 16% answer that they do not know. According to the average figures, 28% of the respondents (OECD-11 - 20%) report a period of up to 1 week, 40% - 1-6 months (OECD-11 - 43%), 23% - 6 months and more (OECD-11 - 18%) And 14% answer "I don't know". Based on the given results, we can say that the degree of financial stability in Georgia is low due to the existence of a financial buffer, and unpredictable shocks can create significant difficulties in terms of financial inclusion.

Diagram N9

Differences in available financial cushion

Percentages of adults who responded they have a financial cushion to last them (i) One week or less; (ii) Savings between 1 month and 6 months; and (iii) Savings of 6 months or above; and (iv) answers with don't know. Sorted by the size of the gap between (iii) and (i)

Note: Malta and Thailand did not ask this question in their surveys and are not in this figure. The OECD member countries in the sample are: Austria, Colombia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Korea, Poland, Portugal and Slovenia.

Regarding the element of taking control of money, which involves tracking cash flows to balance income and expenses, 71.4% of the respondents in Georgia control cash flows, and the average figure is 67.2%.

The cost-conscious element involves assessing needs and affordability in procurement. 70.6% of the respondents in Georgia act according to this principle when making decisions, and the average figure is 71.1%.

In terms of financial deficit, 55.7% of the respondents in Georgia experience financial deficit, and the average indicator is 35.3%.

When considering the element of financial planning, we must assess the provision of savings. 65.2% of the respondents in Georgia say that they actively save money, however, this figure drops to 40.4% for achieving long-term financial goals. The average figures are 70.4% and 48.8%, respectively.

To assess fraud awareness, the OECD/INFE survey included 9 questions to which respondents had to answer "yes" or "no". A positive answer is considered as a low degree of awareness.

Table N2

Falling victim to fraud

Percentage of people who responded with YES to each of the questions below

	Accepted advice to invest in a financial product that you later found to be a scam, such as a Ponzi scheme?	Accidentally provided financial information in response to an email or phone call that you later found out was not genuine?	Discovered that someone has used your details to pay for goods without your authorisation?	Queried a transaction listed on your bank or credit card statement that you did not recognise?	Made a formal complaint about the service you have received from a bank or other financial institution?	Tried to open a bank account and been refused for any reason?	Been refused a claim on an insurance product that you expected to cover you?	Complained to a remittance provider about high charges when sending or receiving money?	Lost money as a result of hackers or phishing scams?
Austria	3.2	1.1	1.0	4.8	2.1	0.9	6.1	2.0	0.8
Colombia	13.5	6.8	5.6	4.9	13.2	20.1	9.3	6.2	4.2
Estonia	2.8	1.5	1.5	1.7	1.1	1.9	1.4	0.3	1.2
Germany	5.3	8.1	13.9	15.1	1.3	3.6	8.4	12.1	1.6
Hong Kong, China	1.2	0.9	0.1	3.7	0.3	0.3	0.6	0.1	
Hungary	2.3	1.6	0.8	2.1	1.9	1.4	3.4	4.3	0.9
Indonesia	22.5	11.4	3.7	3.7	2.3	1.7	1.3	1.1	0.9
Italy	4.8	4.4	4.5	7.4	4.8		6.7	6.0	4.3
Korea	3.0	1.8	1.3	3.4	1.6	1.6	1.8	1.8	0.8
Malaysia	15.9	9.0	4.9	5.5	5.7	4.9	3.5	3.3	-
Peru	13.5	7.4	5.0	6.5	11.1	8.8	8.5	7.5	4.1
Poland	3.6	3.3	2.5	1.3	2.8	1.2	1.0	0.7	0.4
Portugal	1.1	1.4	1.9	5.6	2.9	0.9	1.2	0.5	1.1
Bulgaria	4.3	1.4	1.8	1.9	3.8	1.5	2.0	1.1	0.9
Croatia	1.8	1.5	1.5	3.0	1.6	1.0	1.0	2.8	0.9
Georgia	1.6	0.9	0.8	2.7	1.0	6.2	3.9	0.4	1.5
North Macedonia	2.4	1.0	0.6	3.3	3.3	1.6	1.8	1.3	1.3
Moldova	3.4	3.4	1.9	2.8	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.9	2.5
Montenegro	2.3	1.7	0.8	1.7	5.0	1.9	1.7	5.9	0.6
Romania	7.5	6.7	5.3	4.2	6.0	6.0	4.0	5.0	4.1
Average	5.8	3.8	3.0	4.3	3.7	3.5	3.4	3.2	1.8
OECD average	4.4	3.3	3.7	5.1	3.5	3.5	4.4	3.8	1.7

Note: Czech Republic, Russia, Slovenia and Thailand are missing from the chart as they did not ask these questions. The OECD member countries in the sample are: Austria, Colombia, Estonia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Korea, Poland and Portugal.

Table N2 shows the corresponding percentages by countries. As it is clear from the data, there is a high level of awareness in Georgia, because in the case of each question, both on the average and in terms of individual countries, a much lower percentage of positive answers is recorded compared to the majority of them, which can be considered as a result of the information campaign on the protection of consumer rights and fraudulent schemes carried out by the National Bank.

Conclusion

Financial literacy is important for achieving financial inclusion, because financial inclusion involves not only access to resources, but also the provision of quality and diverse financial instruments and to ensure this, the financial sector must have pressure from the public, and the greater the level of public financial education and the ability to make informed choices based on the analysis of alternatives, the greater the likelihood that the degree of financial inclusion will increase.

Research shows a significant correlation between low levels of financial education and high levels of financial stress experienced by individuals when making various financial decisions. A low level of financial education is also associated with a low level of financial sustainability, which is manifested in the lack of savings and, as a result, in the absence of financial buffers, because individuals with a low level of financial education are characterized by reckless behavior and short-term financial views.

A number of important steps have been taken to raise financial education and improve the quality of financial inclusion in Georgia. The consistent policy of the National Bank of Georgia is worth noting to create a healthy financial environment and protect the rights of financial sector consumers, to eliminate the problem of excessive debt.

The high level of awareness about financial fraud in the country also indicates the efforts of the National Bank in the direction of protection of consumer rights and information campaign about fraudulent schemes.

The use of financial technologies in Georgia still remains a challenge and significantly lags behind the regional average, however, current processes create a favorable environment for strengthening work in this direction and improving results.

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